

A Comparative Study of the Implementation of Preschool Education Curriculums in Mongolia, China, and the South Korea

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Abstract

Original Research Article

This study aims to compare and analyze the purposes, content, concepts, and implementation features of national preschool education programs, particularly in Mongolia, People's Republic of China, and the Republic of Korea (South Korea). Existing comparative studies in this field have primarily focused on the content, methodologies, and impacts of preschool programs on child development within the selected countries. However, there is a notable lack of comparative research involving Mongolia.

The present research will examine the preschool education curricula of the three countries through document analysis, observational studies of kindergarten daily activities, and detailed note-taking. By comparing the specific differences in implementation, this study seeks to elucidate the unique features and disparities among the curriculums.

Research findings indicate that while the theoretical concepts, teaching methods, implementation principles, and organizational structures of preschool education programs in the three countries exhibit significant similarities, discrepancies arise in the implementation of classroom activities. According to the research results, to enhance the quality of preschool education in Mongolia, it is essential to reduce the student-to-teacher ratio, alleviate the workload on educators, and promote greater parental involvement and cooperation.

Keywords: Preschool Education Curriculum, Daily Schedule, Implementation

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INTRODUCTION

The main document of the educational institution in any educational system is the curriculum. It can be said that the program is a dynamic process in the sense that it is a reflection of all the changes taking place in the society. Therefore, in a broad sense, the curriculum is defined as "all the experiences that an individual knows and learns not only in school but also in all social environments" (Bilbao et al., 2021). The curriculum is defined as a document that pre-planned and confirmed the way to implement the concept, policy, and goal of any business or industry development in a certain period of time, and the results to be achieved (Davaa, 2012, p.15). There is a student learning curriculum adapted to the awarding of a certain level of education consisting of interconnected components that define the content and organization of learning and training activities aimed at obtaining a certain level of education (Batsaikhan, & Delgerjav, 2019, p.154). As a result of the curriculum implementation, students will

acquire appropriate knowledge, skills, and attitudes. Jadamba explained that "the curriculum has a function that depends on how well it has been able to define the goals and objectives planned to be achieved." a plan developed with management methods and thinking to solve complex problems, or in other words, a version of the content offered by the organization to its students, and the training needs, concepts, goals and objectives are structured as the main content, implementation methods, and assessment (Purevdorj, 2010, p.175).

Previous comparative studies of national preschool education curriculums have examined the purpose, content, and features of it for young children from multiple perspectives. For instance, Yang and Lee (2018, p.1) conducted a study comparing the implementation of preschool education curriculums in four kindergartens across Hong Kong and Xinjiang, two regions characterized by distinct socio-cultural contexts. Similarly, Samuelson, Sheridan, and Williams (2006, p.11) analyzed five

different program types in Sweden—Reggio Emilia, Te Whāriki, Experiential Education, High Scope, and the Swedish National Curriculum—focusing on their impact on children's learning and development. Johnson (1980, p. 93) compared preschool programs for 4 to 6-year-old children in New Zealand and Malaysia, highlighting the rich cultural differences, historical backgrounds, and conceptual frameworks. Additionally, Kim (2016, p. 12) investigated the implementation of sustainable development goals within preschool programs, using South Korea and Australia as case studies. While these studies provide valuable insights into the content and methodologies of preschool curriculums in various countries, there remains a notable gap in comparative research that includes Mongolia.

One of the significant challenges in the effective implementation of preschool education curriculums in Mongolia is the extensive paperwork required from teachers, which consumes a considerable amount of time (Sarantuya & Mongolkhatan, 2017, p. 222). To address this issue, recent curriculum reforms have introduced various initiatives aimed at reducing administrative burdens. For instance, instead of focusing on written reports and documentation, these reforms prioritize the developmental needs of each child, fostering a supportive environment that encourages children to learn and grow at their own pace (Batsaikhan, 2022, p. 236). Furthermore, during the implementation of preschool education curriculums, there is an emphasis on facilitating play, which is crucial for young children's development (Ministry of Education, Culture and Science, 2015, p. 58; Norjkhoro, 2016, p. 236). Unenbayar, Khajidmaa, Tuya (2018, p. 435) conducted a quantitative analysis of kindergarten educational activities, revealing that 71.3% of these activities focused on movement, health, and the arts. It is essential to guide children toward active participation in society from an early age, helping them develop effective communication habits (Odonchimeg & Baigalmaa, 2023, p. 199).

In this research, the implementation of Mongolia's preschool education curriculum was compared with those of two others rapidly developing Asian countries: the People's Republic of China and the Republic of Korea. These nations were selected based on their advancements in preschool education over the past four decades. China has made significant strides in social and economic development, resulting in enhanced quality of early childhood education (Hang & Delgerjav, 2024, p. 254). Republic of Korea recognized as a regional power and a developed nation, uniquely incorporates themes of patriotism, national culture, and customs into its preschool

education curriculum, emphasizing love for one's country and respect for society from an early age (Sog Riun & Myagmar, 2016, p. 281). Additionally, play-based learning is predominantly utilized as the primary teaching methodology in Republic of Korea.

The significance of this study lies in its objective to observe, identify, and learn from the distinctive features and characteristics of preschool education curriculum implementation across the three countries, particularly in relation to daily kindergarten activities.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This comparative study of preschool education programs in three countries was conducted in three distinct stages:

- 1) Document Analysis: The preschool education programs of the three countries were analyzed and compared in various areas, including program goals, objectives, content, implementation methodologies, learning environments, child development assessments, and organizational structures.
- 2) Field Observations: Researchers contacted state-owned kindergartens participating in the study to obtain permission for observations and make necessary preparations. When selecting the kindergartens, factors such as geographical location, population representation, and local characteristics were taken into account.
- 3) Activity Observation: Over a period of 15 days, all activities within the selected kindergartens were observed and recorded. These observations were then compared to the daily activity schedules to assess their alignment.

By comparing the content and structure of the preschool programs in Mongolia and the Republic of Korea, this study identified and analyzed differences in the daily routines of kindergartens using qualitative methods.

Research Results

The following table presents the results of the comparative analysis of preschool education curricula in Mongolia, People's Republic of China, and the Republic of Korea. The comparison focuses on various aspects, including program goals, content, training activities, principles of implementation, learning environments, evaluation methods, and organizational structures.

Table 1. Comparison of Preschool Education Curricula in Mongolia, People's Republic of China, and South Korea

#	Curriculum Content and Structure	Mongolia	People's Republic of China	Republic of Korea (South Korea)
1	Curriculum Name	Guideline for Preschool Education Curriculum	Guideline for 3-6 ages Children's Education and Development.	Curriculum of "Nuri" National Kindergarten

2	The organization that developed and published the preschool education program	Ministry of Education, Culture and Science, 2019	Ministry of Education of the People's Republic of China, 2012	Korean Ministry of Education, 2019
3	Ages	2-5	3-6	3-5
4	Page numbers	108 pages	75 pages	16 pages
5	Curriculum Content	Background Principle Goals and objectives Content Implementation methodology Learning environment Evaluation Adult support Social development Movement and health Language Natural and social environment Mathematics Music and visual arts	Curriculum Content: One. Health Two. Language Three. Society Four. Science Five. Art	Nuri structure and direction Nuri activity - Physical education exercise and health - Communication - Social relations - Art experience - Nature and science
6	Curriculum Learning Areas	Social development Movement and health Language Nature and social environment Simple mathematical concepts Music and visual arts	Health Language Society Science Art	Physical education exercise and health - Communication - Social relations - Art experience - Natural science
7	Curriculum Principles	The goals and objectives of the training program should consider the child's age, cognitive development, and individual characteristics. The curriculum content should be comprehensive and interconnected, promoting the overall development and maturation of the child. Conditions should be established to allow for flexible planning and organization of training, tailored to the specific methodologies employed with each child. Assessment practices should be designed to nurture and support the unique abilities	Emphasize the Integrity of Child Learning and Development: Child development is holistic; therefore, it is essential to focus on the interconnections and integration among various developmental areas and goals. This approach promotes comprehensive child development rather than prioritizing growth in one or more isolated areas. Coordinated development across all domains should be the objective. Respect Individual Differences in Child Development: Early childhood development is a continuous and gradual process, characterized by distinct	The Nuri Curriculum serves as a national framework for children aged 3 to 5, characterized by the following principles: A. Commonality and Diversity: The curriculum promotes a standardized national approach while simultaneously embracing regional, institutional, and individual diversity. B. Comprehensive Development and Well-Being: The curriculum emphasizes the holistic development and happiness of each child. C. Child-Centered and Play-Based Learning: It prioritizes a child-centered and play-based methodology to facilitate learning. D. Fostering Independence and Creativity: The curriculum aims to cultivate independence and creativity in children. E. Collaborative Engagement: It encourages cooperation among children, teachers, administrators, parents, and the community to achieve these objectives.

		<p>and characteristics of each child.</p> <p>Active participation of parents, guardians, and the community should be encouraged, along with support for kindergarten management, fostering the independence and creativity of teachers.</p>	<p>developmental stages. While all children follow a similar trajectory, the pace of development and the timeline for reaching specific milestones can vary significantly. It is crucial to fully understand, respect, and support individual differences in the developmental processes of young children.</p>	
8	Curriculum Content	<p>The content for implementing the goals and objectives of the curriculum is determined by the developmental outcomes of each child. The training program is designed to support the physical, cognitive, and social development of young children across several key learning areas: "Movement and Health," "Language," "Simple Mathematical Concepts," "Natural and Social Environment," and "Music and Visual Arts."</p> <p>Social development will be fostered within each of these learning domains. Mastery of the content in each area will be assessed at three levels, taking into account the child's age and developmental characteristics. Each child's proficiency is categorized into three levels, ranging from basic to advanced. Level I is targeted for children around 2 years old, Level II for those aged 3 to 4 years, and Level III for 5-year-olds. These three levels aim to cultivate the ability and willingness to learn new concepts, building upon the</p>		<p>The main content of the Nuri Program is characterized by the following components:</p> <p>A. Age Appropriateness: The content is tailored for children aged 3 to 5 years.</p> <p>B. Holistic Development: The program encompasses a vision of the individual that includes positive knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values.</p> <p>C. Organizational Structure: The curriculum is organized into five key areas: Physical Health, Relationships, Social Interaction, Artistic Experiences, and Nature Studies.</p> <p>D. Experience-Based Learning: The content is grounded in the lived experiences of children aged 3 to 5 years.</p> <p>E. Curricular Continuity: The program serves as a continuation of the previous 0-2 age curriculum and aligns with the primary education program.</p>

		child's prior knowledge, imagination, and experiences, and applying this understanding in specific contexts.		
9	Curriculum goals and objectives	Every young child will be supported in developing a healthy body, mind, and spirit, while fostering their unique characteristics and creativity. The program aims to enhance physical, cognitive, and social skills, ensuring holistic development.	Every young child will receive support to grow in a healthy body, mind, and spirit, fostering their unique characteristics and creativity while enhancing their physical, cognitive, and social skills.	The goal of the Nuri Program is to support children's physical, mental, and holistic development through play, while laying the foundation for strong character and democratic citizenship. To achieve this, the following specific objectives are established: A. Self-Value and Healthy Lifestyle: Encourage children to recognize their worth and foster a healthy, safe lifestyle. B. Problem-Solving Skills: Develop essential self-problem-solving abilities. C. Imagination and Creativity: Enhance imagination and creativity through curiosity and inquisitiveness. D. Cultural Sensitivity and Aesthetic Appreciation: Foster a sense of beauty and cultural awareness in everyday life. E. Respect and Communication: Cultivate an attitude of respect, care, and effective communication with both people and nature.
10	Curriculum Implementation Methodology	to effectively achieve the program's goals, objectives, and content, alongside understanding the child's learning methods and actions. Teachers must pay particular attention to the individuality of each child's development, assessing the level at which most children are functioning and organizing activities that cater to their needs. Teaching Methods Child-Centered Learning: Recognizing that each child has a unique way of learning, teaching methods should be adaptable to support diverse learning styles.	The content and objectives of the training are guided by the teacher, who provides educational ideas and recommendations to facilitate the learning process.	When organizing teaching and learning activities, the following considerations for the child should be taken into account: A. Freedom to Play: Allow children to participate freely in games based on their interests, ensuring they have fun. B. Play-Based Learning: Engage children through play as a primary mode of teaching. C. Accessible Environments: Provide both indoor and outdoor spaces where children can enjoy a variety of games and activities. D. Active Interaction: Foster active interactions among infants and toddlers, between infants and teachers, and with their environment. E. Integrated Learning: Ensure that the content from the five learning areas is integrated and coherent within the child's experiences. F. Smooth Daily Routines: Adapt rest and daily life activities to meet the individual needs of each child. G. Individualized Teaching: Implement individualized instruction that considers each child's age, developmental stage, disabilities, and background.
11	Learning Environment	The child's learning environment supports holistic development by ensuring safety	Create a Positive Learning Environment: Establish a supportive atmosphere that	

		across all aspects, including the physical, social, and emotional environments.	encourages exploration, fosters creativity, and nurtures positive relationships among children, teachers, and peers.	
12	Child Development Assessment	There are two types of assessment: process assessment and outcome assessment. The assessment is conducted in a three-part format.	Assessment is not mentioned.	The following factors will be considered in the assessment: Program Quality Improvement: Assessments will be planned and conducted to determine and enhance the quality of the Nuri program. Evaluation of Children's Development: The characteristics, progress, and activities of children within the Nuri program will be evaluated. Methodological Appropriateness: Evaluations will employ appropriate methods tailored to the specific objectives of the assessment. Data Utilization: The results of the evaluation will provide valuable data to enhance the understanding of young children and improve the implementation of the Nuri program.
13	Curriculum Implementation Management	Each kindergarten develops its own plan based on its unique concept, aligning developmental activities with the daily routine and the content of the programs. This planning integrates open content that supports children's growth across various areas of study. Additionally, the kindergarten assesses each child's level of development, organizes activities both individually and in groups, and creates specific plans for children with special needs. Furthermore, the involvement of parents and the local community is emphasized through collaborative activities.	Not written.	The Nuri Program will take the following considerations into account when organizing and implementing its activities: A. Daily Schedule: Activities will be held daily from 4 to 5 o'clock. B. Organizational Flexibility: The program can be organized according to specific work and activities. C. Contextual Planning: Plans tailored to the unique circumstances of each organization will be developed and implemented based on the Nuri Program. D. Daily Routine: The daily schedule will be structured to ensure ample time for children's play, including outdoor activities. E. Inclusivity: The program will be organized and implemented without discrimination based on gender, physical characteristics, disabilities, religion, family background, or cultural origin. F. Support for Special Development: Implementation will take into account the special developmental needs and disabilities of children. G. Community and Family Engagement: Activities will emphasize cooperation and participation with families and the wider community. H. Professional Development: Continuous improvement of the Nuri Program will be achieved through professional development training for teachers.

Resources: Ministry of Education, People's Republic of China. (2012). *Guideline for 3-6 ages Children's Education and Development*. China; Ministry of Education, Republic of Korea. (2019). *National Kindergarten Curriculum*. Public Notice No. 2019-189; Ministry of Education, Culture and Science. (2019). *Guideline for Preschool Education Curriculum Implementation*. Ulaanbaatar. Mongolia.

By comparing the content and structure of preschool education programs in Mongolia, China, and South Korea, the Mongolian program details its principles, goals, objectives, content, implementation methodology, organization of the learning environment, developmental evaluation, and the roles of teachers and parents in the learning process. The program in the China outlines its objectives in Section 2, which is further divided into four parts, with each content area supported by one to three specific objectives. The South Korean program also articulates its content, principles, goals, objectives, methodologies, evaluation strategies, and organizational structure for implementation.

While the curricula of the three countries share similar field names, there are notable distinctions. For

instance, the Chinese science curriculum encompasses aspects of both mathematics and the natural and social environment found in Mongolia. Additionally, South Korea features different focuses in two fields of study: communication and social relations. The daily schedule, which serves as the foundation for implementing the preschool education program, has been compared across two kindergartens in each of the three countries. The summarized daily schedules and activities are presented in the following table, highlighting the common aspects of each activity in color.

Table 2. presents a comparative analysis of the implementation of preschool education programs in Mongolia, China, and South Korea, highlighting key aspects of each program's daily schedule and activities.

Table 2. Comparison of Preschool Education Program Implementation in Mongolia, China, and South Korea

Mongolia			China		South Korea	
No	Activates	Time duration	Activates	Time duration	Activates	Time duration
1			Teacher Preparation	07 ⁰⁰ -07 ³⁰		
2	Morning acceptance	08 ⁰⁰ -08 ⁵⁰	Morning acceptance	07 ³⁰ -07 ⁴⁵	Play Time	07 ⁰⁰ ~09 ⁰⁰
3	Health & Hygiene	08 ⁵⁰ -09 ⁰⁰	Morning Excercise Preparation	07 ⁴⁵ - 07 ⁵⁰		
4	Morning Excercise	09 ⁰⁰ - 09 ²⁰	Morning Excercise	07 ⁵⁰ - 08 ⁰⁵		
5	Circle time	09 ²⁰ - 09 ³⁰	Entering tothe Class	08 ⁰⁵ - 08 ¹⁰	Quiet Play & Information of the Day Activities' Schedu le	09 ⁰⁰ ~09 ³⁰
6			Breakfast Preparation	08 ¹⁰ - 08 ²⁰		
7	Breakfast	09 ³⁰ - 09 ⁵⁵	Breakfast	08 ²⁰ - 08 ⁵⁰		
8			Health & Hygiene	08 ⁵⁰ - 09 ⁰⁰		
9	Activities according to 6 Learning Areas	10 ⁰⁰ - 10 ³⁰	Learning Time	09 ⁰⁰ - 09 ³⁰	Free Play & Outdoor Play	09 ³⁰ ~11 ³⁰
10			Drinking Water	09 ³⁰ - 09 ⁴⁰		
11			Team Movement	09 ⁴⁰ - 10 ⁰⁰		
12	Tea & Snack	10 ³⁵ - 10 ⁵⁵	Tea & Snack	10 ⁰⁰ - 10 ¹⁰		
13	Take a Walk/ Outdoor Play	10 ⁵⁵ - 11 ²⁵	Outdoor Excercise	10 ¹⁰ - 10 ⁵⁰		
14			Preparation & Drinking Water	10 ⁵⁰ - 11 ⁰⁰	Break & Bathroom	11 ³⁰ ~11 ⁴⁰
15			Excercise before Lunch	11 ⁰⁰ - 11 ¹⁵		
16	Health & Hygiene	11 ³⁰ - 11 ⁵⁰	Health & Hygiene	11 ¹⁵ - 11 ²⁰		
17	Lunch	12 ⁰⁵ - 12 ⁴⁵	Lunch	11 ²⁰ - 11 ⁵⁰	Lunch, tooth wash and rest	11 ⁴⁰ ~12 ³⁰
18	Health & Hygiene	12 ⁴⁵ - 12 ⁵⁵	Health & Hygiene	11 ⁵⁰ - 12 ⁰⁰	Indoor Play	
19	Nap Time	13 ⁰⁰ - 15 ⁰⁰	Nap Time	12 ⁰⁰ - 14 ²⁰	Class / Group Activities	12 ³⁰ ~12 ⁵⁰
20			Preparation for getting up	14 ²⁰ - 15 ⁰⁰	Hagwon class	12 ⁵⁰ ~13 ⁰⁰
21	Hygiene	15 ⁰⁰ - 15 ³⁰	Corner Movement	15 ⁰⁰ - 15 ⁵⁰		

22			Preparation/Drinking water	15 ⁵⁰ - 16 ⁰⁰	Break/Play Introduction	13 ⁰⁰ ~13 ²⁰
23			Outdoor Activities	16 ⁰⁰ - 16 ⁵⁰	Outdoor/indoor Play	13 ²⁰ ~14 ⁰⁰
24			Preparation for Snack	16 ⁵⁰ - 16 ⁵⁵	Special Activities	14 ⁰⁰ ~15 ⁰⁰
25	Snack	15 ³⁰ - 16 ⁰⁰	Snack	16 ⁵⁵ - 17 ²⁰	Snack	15 ⁰⁰ ~15 ³⁰
26	Development Activities	16 ⁰⁰ - 16 ³⁰			Class/Small group Play & Cleaning	15 ³⁰ ~16 ⁰⁰
27			Preparation for Leaving	17 ²⁰ - 17 ³⁰		
28	Leaving	16 ³⁰ - 17 ³⁰	Leaving	17 ³⁰ -17 ⁴⁵	Solitude Play & Leaving	16 ⁰⁰ ~20 ⁰⁰

When examining the daily routines from a structural perspective, the programs in Mongolia and China share similarities, including morning reception, morning exercise, breakfast, study time, lunch, nap time, and evening meals. In contrast, South Korea's program provides various opportunities for play, incorporating designated times for games, both indoors and outdoors, as well as in class, in small groups, and individually.

Regarding the characteristics and differences in daily activities among kindergartens in the three countries, the kindergarten in Mongolia's capital features 16 activities, with a focus on developmental and health-related activities that set it apart from the other two countries. Chinese kindergartens offer a more extensive

schedule, with 27 activities that include 2 hours of outdoor play. In China, a child's daily water intake is determined based on their body mass index, and detailed records of water consumption are maintained. South Korean kindergartens have 14 activities, emphasizing developmental play through games, which do not include designated nap times and thus occupy a larger portion of the daily schedule.

Table 3. outlines the distinct features and differences in the implementation of preschool education programs across Mongolia, China, and South Korea, highlighting key aspects of each program's structure and daily activities.

Table 3. Features and Differences in the Implementation of Preschool Education Programs in Mongolia, China, and South Korea

#	Activities	Mongolia	People's Republic of China	Republic of Korea (South Korea)
1	Duration of Morning Acceptance	60 minutes	15 minutes - Strict	Less than 30 minutes
2	Greeting with the Children	Greet and Talk	Greet with a Hug	Greet
3	Morning Acceptance Place	At the class door	Inside the kindergarten yard, delivered. No outsiders are allowed in the class.	Kindergarten Outdoor Areas
4	Morning Exercise	Exercises in the classroom	Exercises outdoor	n/a
5	Learning Activities	Provide knowledge and skills in 6 learning areas.	Provide knowledge and skills in 5 learning areas.	Provide knowledge and skills in 5 learning areas.
6	Hygiene & Health	Although not specified in the daily schedule, it typically takes an average of 5 minutes to transition from one activity to another.	The duration for activities is specified in detail, and water consumption is carefully monitored and recorded. During this time, the teacher engages in conversation with the children to encourage communication and interaction.	Children use the toilet, wash their hands, and drink water while playing in the classroom. They are encouraged to hydrate before going outside to play and prior to lunchtime.

7	Outdoor Activities	There is a picnic scheduled, but its implementation may vary based on the number of children in the class and the prevailing weather conditions.	Children are taken outside three times a day for physical exercise or play activities.	When the weather is favorable, we conduct exercise sessions outdoors; otherwise, we organize activities and games within the classroom.
8	Nap time	Due to the limited space in the kindergarten, children sleep in close proximity to one another.	The classroom can be monitored to ensure that children are sleeping properly. If a child is unable to sleep, they can be relocated to another area to engage in play activities.	There is no designated sleep time. If a child feels sleepy and needs to rest, they can do so in the lounge.
9	Free activities	Children will be told stories and can play with their favorite games.	This activity is referred to as 'Corner Movement'.	The teacher observes the child and provides support during play, without giving specific game instructions.
10	Lunch	Lunch includes 1 st and 2 nd sets and teachers serve.	Before lunch always explains what ingredients are included.	Mostly three kinds of food included: Soup, Rice and Fruits.
11	Main Activities	Intended learning activities.	Preferred physical development and health.	Theatre drama id presented based on children's interest.
12	Physical Education and Movement	Morning exercise Walk Free play Physical activities	Morning exercise Team movement Outdoor physical activities Movement before lunch Corner movement	Outdoor play Play Safety
13	Leaving time	1 hour depending on traffic and other issues.	Within 15 minutes – strict on time.	Ordinary day children leave at 2 pm. If there is piano and Hagwon children leave at 4 pm.
14	Classroom Environment	The budget is insufficient, so classrooms are decorated with the assistance of parents and donors.	The budget is sufficient, and all necessary resources are available.	Classrooms are decorated in diverse ways to celebrate children's holidays.
15	Children's Ratio	The number of children in a class is around 25, although it often exceeds.	30 children in one classroom	The class size is capped at a maximum of 15 children for the three-year-old class, 20 for the four-year-old class, and 23 for the five-year-old class.
16	Teachers	1 Teacher, 1 Assistant teacher	2 Teachers, 1 Assistant teacher	1 Teacher

Resources: Ministry of Education, People's Republic of China. (2012). *Guideline for 3-6 ages Children's Education and Development*. China; Ministry of Education, Republic of Korea. (2019). *National Kindergarten Curriculum*. Public Notice No. 2019-189; Ministry of Education, Culture and Science. (2019). *Guideline for Preschool Education Curriculum Implementation*. Ulaanbaatar. Mongolia.

As illustrated in the table, the daily activities in kindergartens in Mongolia and China are interconnected from the child's reception to their dismissal. The comparison reveals that in Mongolian kindergartens, the duration of activities that promote physical development and health, such as morning exercise and walks, tends to be relatively short, with a greater emphasis on structured and intentional organization.

In Chinese kindergartens, children's daily water intake is carefully monitored; kindergartens integrate this

practice into their routines and maintain detailed records of consumption. Transitioning from one activity to another is marked by a mandatory preparation period, which helps children learn to manage their time effectively. Additionally, by explaining the nutritional value of food, educators instil healthy eating habits from an early age, allowing for more time dedicated to physical activities.

In South Korea, the program encourages children to engage in learning activities through play, allowing them to make choices, explore their interests, and create

based on their own ideas.

DISCUSSION

Despite differences in socio-economic conditions and cultural contexts, the three countries exhibit similarities in their implementation of preschool education programs, particularly regarding program content, learning areas, and focus. The programs in Mongolia and South Korea are both concise and detailed, while the Chinese program offers a more general structure.

In Mongolia and South Korea, substantial budgets are allocated to preschool education, resulting in learning environments and facilities that cater to children's preferences and provide a variety of toys. While the overarching goal of preschool education in Mongolia and China is to support the comprehensive development of young children, South Korea's Nuri program specifically emphasizes development and learning through play. Its goals focus on personal development, which includes: 1. Recognizing one's worth and fostering a healthy and safe lifestyle; 2. Developing basic problem-solving skills; 3. Cultivating imagination and creativity through curiosity; 4. Appreciating beauty and cultural sensitivity in everyday life; 5. Fostering respect, care, and communication with people and nature.

These goals illustrate that South Korea's preschool education program not only supports overall child development but also emphasizes personal growth, moral education, and social communication skills. In contrast, Mongolia's program incorporates a unified learning methodology in its implementation; however, the training is primarily based on specific activity topics. In South Korea, there is a notable emphasis on aligning training activities with children's interests and developmental characteristics within a unified educational framework.

When analyzing the implementation of preschool education programs through observations of daily routines in kindergartens across the three countries, several key differences emerge. In Mongolian kindergartens, 16 activities are planned to support children's development. In contrast, Chinese kindergartens schedule 27 activities focused on physical activity and exercise, while South Korean kindergartens organize 14 distinct activities.

In all three contexts, child-centered activities facilitate peer learning. However, there are notable distinctions in focus: Mongolia's preschool education activities primarily aim to impart knowledge and skills to children. In China, daily activities emphasize physical development, particularly through outdoor play. Conversely, South Korean kindergartens prioritize a diverse range of play and learning methods, ensuring that activities are inclusive and non-discriminatory. The South Korean program is designed to accommodate children's various backgrounds and special developmental needs, creating an advantageous environment for all children.

CONCLUSION

By comparing the preschool curricula of Mongolia, China, and South Korea at the document level, it becomes evident that the philosophies of these national

programs vary according to each country's social, economic, political, and cultural traditions. Through a review of comparative research sources on preschool education programs, aimed to deepen the understanding of the structure and content of these programs and their daily activities in kindergartens. The findings were analyzed in detail.

The analysis revealed that while the content, methodology, theoretical frameworks, implementation principles, and organization of the Mongolian preschool education curriculum share similarities with those of the two Asian countries, several challenges persist in Mongolia. Specifically, the number of children in kindergarten groups exceeds the established standards, and the learning environments are often constrained by limited space and resources. Although the daily schedule includes designated time for outdoor activities, the poor quality of outdoor play environments in Ulaanbaatar city's kindergartens negatively impacts the quality of educational activities that are intended to support comprehensive child development.

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